

High Seas Fisheries and Ocean carbon – An interactive online workshop: Summary workshop report

27th February 2024, 14.00 – 18.00 CET/13.00 – 17.00 GMT

Online Teams Meeting

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Stakeholder Sign-Up Sheet: <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUsignup>

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Executive Summary

The Marine Institute hosted an online stakeholder workshop, on the 27th February 2024, focused on ocean carbon interactions with 'high seas' fishing in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ). It was attended by 18 participants.

The workshop had a dedicated half-day to discuss ocean carbon and its interaction with high seas fisheries. Before the workshop, a survey on initial perceptions of the interactions of ocean carbon, climate change, and fisheries was sent to participants. At the workshop, a series of presentations introduced the OceanICU project, an overview of the pre-workshop survey results, and a 'primer' on ocean carbon. Time was provided for open discussion (Q&A) around the topics presented. This was followed by an interactive session building a conceptual model of ocean carbon and fisheries social-ecological system.

Key topics that emerged can be parsed into the following themes:

- **Fisheries and Climate Change:** The impacts of climate change on fisheries, how carbon will affect food-webs (and the implications for fisheries), and how fisheries can adapt to climate change.
- **Fishing in the wider context of the global carbon cycle:** How fishing activity compares to other marine activities (e.g. oil and gas activities); and land-based activities (e.g. farming) in terms of carbon footprint.
- **Food security and fishing livelihoods:** Full consideration of management trade-offs and impacts, including consideration of the services provided by fisheries (e.g. seafood/ food security, employment, ancillary industries).
- **Sustainable fishing practices and implications for the carbon cycle:** How different fleets and sustainability practices (e.g. via certification) can affect carbon impacts/footprint.
- **Efficiency in fishing:** How improved sustainability and efficiency (e.g. via gears, behaviours, etc.) may affect or mitigate carbon impacts/footprint.
- **Data/knowledge gaps:** Research is required to address the many remaining knowledge gaps, particularly relating to evidence on the links between fishing and the ocean carbon cycle/ biological carbon pump.

The discussions surrounding the exercises will inform the ongoing research trajectories in the OceanICU. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the stakeholder group.

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1. Workshop Goals and Set-Up

1.1 Goals

The relationship between fishing activity and ocean carbon is complicated and somewhat controversial. The ocean takes up about 25% of the carbon we add to the atmosphere, slowing climate change. Various things affect this uptake, yet the overall relationship between fishing, marine carbon and climate change are not well known or understood. OceanICU, a Horizon Europe international collaborative project, is working to address these issues. OceanICU focuses on improving understanding of the interactions and potential effects of industrial fishing on ocean carbon, and assessing if those effects are large enough to affect with ocean carbon uptake and climate change.

This report details the first stakeholder workshop with high seas fishery stakeholders as part of this project. The goal of this workshop was to document stakeholder understanding of the links between high seas fishing and ocean carbon.

1.2 Intended Outcomes

The workshop aimed to identify knowledge gaps, areas of interest or need, and potential vulnerabilities and opportunities for intervention relating to high seas fisheries and ocean carbon. This was achieved by carrying out interactive exercises including a pre-workshop survey, live brainstorming, open discussion and the co-production of a mental model of the fisheries-carbon system, including the elements that should be included in such a system, and the types of links between those elements.

The outcomes will inform the direction of research going forward in OceanICU, specifically feeding into developing future scenarios and management/policy questions that are relevant to stakeholder needs, attempting to fill knowledge gaps, and providing input to the development of decision support tools and outputs from the project. We intend to build on the outputs of this workshop with future stakeholder engagement events and workshops.

1.3 Meeting Set-Up

The meeting was hosted online via teams with collaborative notetaking via a Sharepoint word document. Participants were provided with a participant information sheet and asked to fill in a consent form in advance of the workshop to comply with GDPR and good ethical scientific practice.

In advance of the workshop, participants were invited to fill out a survey on ocean carbon which gathered some of their initial perceptions of ocean carbon and the links with climate change and fishing. Results were presented at the meeting.

The meeting was recorded for note-taking purposes only. Chatham house rules (information disclosed during a meeting may be reported by those present, but the source of that information may not be explicitly or implicitly identified) was used to ensure open dialogue. Participants were encouraged to contribute with respect in whichever way they were comfortable to do so (speaking up, posting in the Teams chat, or writing directly in the notes document). Additional resources were provided to participants via Sharepoint and were available for editing/contributing one-week post-meeting.

The OceanICU project, goals and some background on ocean carbon were presented to provide context and ensure a common starting point.

1.4 Participant profile

A total of 22 individuals engaged with the survey and/or workshop. 18 attended the workshop (Figures 1.1, 1.2), with 20 people having completed the survey in advance of the workshop. The workshop was attended by individuals from the fishing industry and their representatives, managers and responsible authorities, advisory bodies, NGOs and academia (Figure 1.1). Participants from the fishing industry and responsible authorities/management had the greatest representation at the workshop, each forming 33% of the group.

Figure 1.1 High Seas Fisheries Attendees and Survey participants (for terms see glossary, Appendix 7.2)

Figure 1.2 Participant profile of attendees at the workshop¹. Fishing industry includes fishers, producers and their representatives. Participant profile of the survey responses varies slightly from this².

¹ One individual was associated with both Academic/Research and an NGO, but was assigned to academia here as their primary affiliation. One individual was associated with Management/Responsible Authority and Academic/Research and was assigned to Management/Responsible Authority here.

² Four individuals (3 from Fishing industry and 1 Advisory Body) completed the survey but did not attend the workshop. Two people (1 from Advisory Body and 1 from Fishing Industry) attended the workshop but did not complete the survey. Survey participant profile was: Fishing Industry: 8 individuals, 40%; Management/Responsible Authority: 6 individuals, 30%; Academic/Research: 3 individuals, 15%; Advisory Body: 2 individuals, 10%; NGO: 1 individual, 5%.

2. Introduction

2.1 The OceanICU project

Dr Debbi Pedreschi gave an introduction to the OceanICU project. OceanICU is a Pan-European project funded by Horizon Europe and UKRI running from November 2022 to October 2027. It has a consortium of 31 partners across 15 countries. The overall project aim is to produce new data, information and understanding on the role of the ocean in the global carbon cycle. Demands for ocean resources such as food from fish, materials such as trace metals, and blue energy (wind, wave, tidal) are increasing. These increasing demands may affect the uptake of carbon by the ocean due to changes in emissions, industrial processes, and climate change itself. OceanICU recognises the need for knowledge and tools to support decisions makers, managers, and ocean users manage ocean resources, and understand how their interactions with the ocean may affect ocean carbon and hence climate change.

OceanICU is developing new tools that include parameters relevant to management and industry (Figure 2.1). As such, we aim to establish current understanding, perceptions, and needs of stakeholders in relation to oceanic carbon and identify key emerging threats and trajectories. This information will then be used to define scenarios of interest and societal relevance for use in a decision-support tool (DST), and to inform an oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, scenarios, and trade-offs, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services. As part of this, we will produce a multi-sectoral, multi-pressure oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally-relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services.

Figure 2.1 Overview of processes considered in the OceanICU project.

2.2 Links between ocean carbon and high seas fisheries

Prof. David Reid and Dr Fiona Culhane introduced some of the relevant points concerning the links between ocean carbon and high seas fisheries. High seas are the areas of the ocean beyond national jurisdiction and make up nearly 60% of the global ocean (Carmine et al., 2020). High seas sediment store around 51% of ocean carbon stocks (Atwood et al., 2020). One of the primary sectors in the high seas is fishing; this is composed mainly of pelagic fisheries (Carmine et al., 2020).

The key themes addressed in the part of the workshop were:

- Fish and the biological carbon pump
- Carbon emissions from fuel use in fishing
- Fishing and carbon release from the seafloor
- Emerging/expanding industries that have a role in relation to carbon or climate change

Prof. Reid described our current understanding of where organic and inorganic carbon is stored in the ocean. He emphasised that the amount of carbon stored in all marine biomass is small (5Gt), compared to e.g. 2200Gt stored in marine sediments (ICES, 2024). Despite this relatively small amount of stored carbon, marine animals can sequester much more (800Gt) through respiration, migration and faecal matter (Pinti et al., 2023). 35% of this 800Gt is by mesopelagic fish.

The emissions from fuel use in fishing are reasonably well understood from the available data. Different types of fishing have different fuel use intensities (Parker in Ziegler & Hornborg, 2023). There are also numerous ways to improve fuel use efficiency, e.g. through using low drag gears, changing fishing behaviour, making engines more efficient, using green fuels, and maintaining healthier fish stocks.

An example from Mouillot et al. (2023) on tuna fisheries was shown, where fuel use and the biological carbon pump interact. This example showed that tuna populations, which were mainly CO₂ sinks in the 1980s, have partly become CO₂ sources in the 2000s due to higher exploitation rates and decreasing stock sizes, which have reduced the sinking of dead carcasses, and led to increased fuel consumption to reach more remote areas.

Current research on the impact of bottom trawling on the release of carbon from sediments was also discussed. This is an emerging area of research which is creating some contention. While it is generally accepted that bottom trawling can cause the release of carbon from sediments, there is no consensus on what the extent of this is. For example, Sala et al., (2021) reported that bottom trawling releases the equivalent of 15-20% of atmospheric CO₂. However, using different modelling assumptions, Hiddink et al. (2023) found this to be over-estimated by two to three orders of magnitude. Another study by Epstein et al., (2022) carried out a review that showed mixed results in sediment organic carbon stocks following trawling disturbance.

2.3 Future trajectories

Dr Culhane presented some of the emerging industries that may interact with ocean carbon and high seas fisheries. These activities are developing in the context of food security, green-technology mineral requirements, and on-going climate change trajectories. Emerging industries include the potential development of fisheries of Mesopelagic species, Deep-sea mining and industrial Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR).

Interactions between fisheries, ocean carbon and emerging industries have implications for ecosystem service trade-offs including in relation to food security and fishing livelihoods; green technology mineral requirements; both natural and enhanced carbon capture and storage; as well as nature for nature's sake and biodiversity.

2.4 Discussion: Ocean Carbon and Fisheries

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the Marine Institute (MI)/OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- How does Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC) relate to other elements on the slide (slide 20)? MI: it's the physical carbon pump. There is both a biological carbon pump and a physical carbon pump³.
- What about bacteria and viruses? Don't they make up a large biomass of carbon sequestration in the sea? MI: this study is just about animals, not bacteria and viruses. Most biomass of carbon sequestered is due to phytoplankton. *Added: a team in the project is considering the role of the Microbial Carbon Pump in their models.*
- What do you mean by the terms industrial fishing and high seas fisheries? All North Atlantic fisheries could be called industrial. MI: Industrial fisheries = any fisheries that aren't small scale, artisanal type fisheries. We want to understand the role of fisheries in areas beyond national jurisdiction in the marine biological carbon pump process. There are a lot of unknowns and we want to investigate them to understand the scale. We are also committed [*through the project*] to looking at deep sea mining but are open to looking at other areas (e.g. shipping, offshore renewable energy). The focus is to understand the scale of the activities, and whether they are negligible or not.
- How widely are you looking at the whole carbon system? Are you looking at the oceans and terrestrial? It is important to look at 1kg of carbon compared to 1kg of protein for human consumption. When you remove fish from the sea, you are removing carbon. This carbon doesn't disappear; it goes into human beings. What about the terrestrial carbon cycle? MI: This is a very valid point however, our focus is the marine, because the vast majority of the knowledge that already exists is terrestrial, and the marine is the main knowledge gap. OceanICU also intends to feed into IPCC global estimates, so there will be some connections but we aren't studying terrestrial carbon cycle. We are interested in socio-economic impacts of the marine carbon cycle on processors, fishing communities impacted etc. [*which occur on land*]. Fish does go into human bodies and is cycled on land but the carbon is still removed from the marine realm, disrupting the cycle.
- Are you looking at the krill in relation to mesopelagic fisheries? Big biomass, quite small allowances. MI: It is not a specific focus of this work as yet. There is little knowledge in relation to mesopelagics so we must be careful in drawing conclusions. We need more information to even know if mesopelagic fisheries are biologically, ecologically, economically and sociologically sustainable.
- We want to know the impact on both marine and terrestrial cycles but we need to understand how it will affect and which one it is better to affect. This work is really valuable as it fills in the gap but at policy level in governance they need to look at both marine and terrestrial cycles.

³ There is an OceanICU webinar available to watch on the topic of whether ocean carbon uptake will continue primarily as an abiotic process <https://ocean-icu.eu/webinars/oceanicu-webinar-4/>

- In high seas you're considering the pelagic because of possible extraction of small pelagic species, do we know what portion of the ocean floor sediment is affected by these fisheries? MI: We have split our focus into open ocean pelagics and shelf sea fisheries. In terms of area, shelf fisheries represent a small portion compared to pelagic systems. However, we don't understand the biological carbon pump on the shelf [*most models are global or offshore models*], it's much more complicated and dynamic system [*than pelagic systems*]. OceanICU is currently working to build understanding of how fishing interacts with the carbon storage on the shelf.
- Sala et al has been heavily rebuked and criticised for not following proper scientific procedure, so why is it still being cited? MI: We aren't trying to quote Sala as correct, we are highlighting that it gets quoted by the press and that message gets out there. Sala says one thing, Hiddink says the opposite, and usually the answer is something in between. We are trying to find the part in between.
- What's the ratio between disturbance of the ocean floor in the shelf area between fishing and storms. After storms it's very apparent that the ocean floor has been disturbed a long way into the sea and takes a long time to settle after the storms are abated. MI: Storms have been occurring for millions of years and large scale fishing for just a thousand or so. We are looking at the difference/impact made by the addition of fishing to identify the anthropogenic impact. Scale matters: if the disturbance by storms is 100 or 1000 times more than the disturbance of fisheries, the fishing won't come out as a big thing. If fishing damage is much more, then we need to know that, and which gears impact most. We are assuming storminess is unlikely to affect the ocean floor in high seas fisheries, if that's a mistake, please let us know and we will look into it.
- There are other elements that are unknown and not taken into account in Sala analysis: e.g. what is the role of bioturbation? What about storms that are a great deal responsible of putting sediment in suspension? In the EU we have a big shelf where we fish; a lot of organic material which is always coming from the land to the shelf. In some sense, fishing on the seabed will contribute to displace the sediment material to the continental shelf slope, and to deep, where carbon is stored. Are those effects also studied? It could also go against the theory in Sala. MI: What was discussed regarding trawling, storms etc., redistributing sediment are all valid and will be looked at. The core of the group that we are working with in OceanICU are oceanographers and biogeochemical modellers, so this is at the centre of what they do, they are looking at global bioturbation aspects. It's challenging to bring this [*more local and small-scale*] information into their global models, but we are trying to address this.
- You said you wouldn't be against looking at another industry like shipping but didn't mention wind farms. This also probably has an impact on the sea floor and fish populations. MI: We will be looking for your suggestions on other areas to look into, so we are open to taking this into account.
- When speaking about terrestrial aspects, all trade-offs should be taken into account. Human beings need to eat, if it isn't fish it will be other proteins or vegetables. Fish protein has the smallest carbon footprint at the moment. This all needs to be taken into account. Comparisons should be undertaken with other sources of protein. MI: We are trying to get a better handle on the entire carbon footprint so that what we have can be compared to terrestrial estimates. A lot of the work that has been done [*to date on protein comparisons*] doesn't take into account interactions with the biological carbon pump. We are interested in these interactions and improving our understanding of the mechanisms and processes that are underpinning them.
- There was an article in "science advances" studying historical fisheries data concluding that industrial fisheries did remove million tonnes of carbon from the ocean by fishing. However, taking into account all the processes involved in the carbon cycle, and after calculations were made on an average annual basis, the blue carbon cost of fishing for large pelagic fish was finally only about

0.02% of the total amount of carbon stored each year in the oceans, which is negligible. How are you planning to study these various aspects not to be misleading about the tuna fisheries? MI: The relative percentages don't sound very high but it's also important to look at the absolute amounts. We don't intend to be misleading and will work hard not to be. We have these kinds of workshops to present anything we are developing to you so you can give us feedback and let us know if something should be presented in a different way or appears misleading.

- Marine mammals are not really fished but are harvested in some areas, and interact with fisheries by being bycatch, tangled in gear etc. Do you have any intention of bringing marine mammals into the discussion on fisheries carbon interactions? MI: The paper we presented didn't take marine mammals (MM) into account, however OceanICU will take mammals into account. For example one of our colleagues works on whale poo and the role it plays in carbon cycling⁴. There is also potential for mammals to be taken into account in the shelf seas ecosystem models and the conceptual models.
- Acidification is potentially something to be worried about in rivers, lakes, coastal fisheries etc. rather than high seas. Is your project just on high seas and not coastal fisheries? MI: Today's workshop is focussed on high seas, we have another stakeholder meeting on shelf seas coming up. Not sure about acidification in the shelf seas models, but it is being taken into account in the large scale oceanic models.
- When we are talking about the amount of sequestration that marine organisms are responsible for, do we know the time scale we are taking about? How long will the carbon be there for? If it's a recurrent cycle, how long is the cycle? *Added: the presented paper states that the sequestration time scale is ~250 years (Pinti et al., 2023; <https://bq.copernicus.org/articles/20/997/2023/#bib1.bibx11>).*

⁴ <https://ocean-icu.eu/blogs/how-important-are-whales-in-the-oceanic-carbon-cycle-scientists-are-looking-for-the-answer/>

3. Results

3.1 Pre-Workshop Survey

A survey consisting of 13 questions about ocean carbon and 6 questions about the respondents was distributed online in advance of the workshop as part of the formal registration process for the workshop. The survey was hosted on the platform SurveyMonkey. It was designed to get initial perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon, prime the participants to start thinking about the links between fishing and ocean carbon, and assess potential knowledge gaps to prepare presentations for the workshop itself.

The first question asked what people think of when they hear the term ‘*ocean carbon*’ (Box 3.1). OceanICU takes the starting point that the ocean plays a crucial role in regulating the global climate, by taking up 25% of atmospheric CO₂ and by storing large amounts of carbon, much of it through the processes of the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP); and that the BCP is much more complex than previously thought. While only one respondent explicitly mentioned the BCP in answer to this question, the role of living part of the ocean was mentioned directly (e.g. ‘*carbon stored in aquatic animals and seabed*’) or indirectly (e.g. ‘*carbonate sediment*’) 4 times. However, many of the responses given capture processes related to the BCP, including the ocean as a source and sink of carbon and the marine carbon cycle in general. Other themes that emerged included those related to climate change, ocean acidification and the ocean as a solution to climate change. The role of industry and emissions was also mentioned, in addition to the relevant time scales of different processes of the ocean carbon cycle.

Box 3.1 Themes of the responses to the question: “*What comes to mind when you hear the term ocean carbon?*” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 19 respondents.

- The ocean and/or ocean life as a sink for carbon and/or atmospheric CO₂ (9)
- Marine carbon (organic and inorganic) cycle/carbon balance in ocean (4)
- Biological carbon pump and/or role of living ocean organisms (4)
- Mitigation, decarbonisation, energy transition (4)
- Climate change (3)
- Ocean acidification (3)
- Industry and emissions (3)
- Timescale of carbon sequestration and storage (3)
- The ocean and ocean life as a source for carbon and/or atmospheric CO₂ (2)
- Complexity and uncertainty (1)
- Marine ecosystem impacts (1)
- Not something we need to consider (1)

Ninety-four percent of respondents thought that the ocean is extremely or very important for helping us to manage or improve climate change (Figure 3.1). One respondent emphasised that this is because wild fish are a low carbon food source compared to other animal protein, and therefore a key way to reduce the carbon footprint of food generally. Two respondents mentioned the need to reduce emissions, with one highlighting the need for a focus on terrestrial policy in relation to this, rather than focussing on enhancing the ocean as a carbon sink.

Figure 3.1 Responses to the question: “How important is the ocean for helping us to manage or improve climate change?” (17 respondents)

41% of respondents thought that the links between carbon and fishing are moderately important for understanding the Biological Carbon Pump and/or climate change, while 29% thought these links have a lot of importance (Figure 3.2). Two respondents noted a lack of evidence in this area, and another noted that fisheries can be an important source of data. Two respondents perceived the impacts of fishing as not being too big, with one of these stressing that land-based activities have greater impacts.

Figure 3.2 Responses to the question: “How important are the links between carbon and fishing for understanding the Biological Carbon Pump and/or climate change?” (17 respondents)

In terms of the ways participants thought ocean carbon affects fishing, the most common responses related to climate change and its impacts of fish and fisheries (Box 3.2). The impacts of management of ocean carbon on fisheries was also raised, as well as the need for more evidence or knowledge on the links. In terms of how fishing affects ocean carbon, the most common response related to seabed disturbance and the release of carbon from the sediment (Box 3.3). Other responses included those related to food web changes and the carbon cycle more broadly, emissions, management and again the need for evidence.

Box 3.2 Themes of the responses to the question: “In what ways do you think ocean carbon affects fishing?” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 17 responses.

- Impacts of climate change, including temperature, acidification and weather, on fish and fisheries, including distribution, behaviour and abundance of fish and foodwebs (10)
- Impacts to management of fishing (4)
- More evidence/knowledge needed (3)
- Need for adaption and mitigation of climate change impacts for resilience of the fishing industry (1)
- Carbon as the source of ocean life and fishery resources (1)

Box 3.3 Themes of the responses to the question: “*In what ways do you think fishing affects ocean carbon?*” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 18 responses.

- Disturbance of seabed due to trawling and other factors, with potential release of carbon from sediments (6)
- Changes to the food web, including removal of biomass that may transfer carbon to depth, disturbance of trophic cascades, bycatch, predator-prey dynamics (5)
- Implications (or lack of) for broader carbon cycle generally (5)
- Uncertainty or lack of evidence on the links (4)
- Carbon emissions to atmosphere and fuel use (4)
- Implications for management including MPAs and restricted fishing in certain habitats, carbon credits and rebuilding stocks (3)
- Fishing as a low carbon industry compared to others (2)
- Fishing as an essential supply of protein (1)
- Damage to carbon fishing organisms (1)

53% of respondents are moderately concerned about the carbon footprint of fishing (Figure 3.3). Two respondents stated that more evidence is needed in relation to this point. Two others emphasised the need to specify the type of fishing, as pelagic, for example has low carbon intensity, especially in comparison to other animal proteins. Another respondent also put fishing in the wider context, i.e. fishing represents 0.1-0.5% of total global emissions⁵. They also highlighted the EU fleet as an example of how reducing the fleet and investments in efficiency (in relation to engines, refrigeration, propellers) can further reduce emissions, with the EU reducing their fleet emissions by 52% between 2000 and 2020. This respondent acknowledged that not all fleets are reducing emissions, and in some cases are continuously increasing theirs. Fuel use was considered the largest contributor to the fishing industries’ carbon footprint (Box 3.4), but the type of gear, disturbance to the seabed, distance travelled, efficiency of vessels and the market chain were all factors mentioned as being important.

Figure 3.3 Responses to the question: “*How concerned are you about the carbon footprint of fishing?*” (17 responses).

⁵ <https://unctad.org/publication/energy-transition-fishing-fleets-opportunities-and-challenges-developing-countries>

Box 3.4 Themes of the responses to the question: “*What aspect of fishing do you think are most important for its carbon footprint?*” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 17 responses.

- Fuel use and CO2 emissions from the vessel, the need for low carbon fuels (10)
- Type of gear (4)
- Sediment disturbance and interactions with seabed (4)
- Distance travelled (3)
- Efficiency of the vessels, need for technological improvements and maintenance (3)
- Processing, distribution and transportation in the market chain (3)
- Effort and continuation (2)
- Need for circular economy (1)
- Refrigerant leakage (1)
- Impacts to long-lived organisms that store carbon (1)
- Don’t know (1)

When thinking about living organisms that are important for capturing and storing carbon, the most common response (6 respondents) was plankton and vulnerable marine ecosystems (Box 3.5).

69% of respondents were only a little or moderately concerned about removing fish or other animals, plants and algae from the ocean in relation to removing ocean carbon (Figure 3.4). Two respondents noted the need for more research in relation to this question. One considered the balance of carbon inputs to the system (e.g. through land and river sediments) versus the removals. The other asked where does the carbon ultimately end up. One respondent also emphasised the need for discussions about climate and carbon to consider the big picture in relation to food production, while continuing to minimise the environmental impacts of fishing.

Box 3.5 Themes of the responses to the question: “*What comes to mind when you think about the living organisms important for capturing and storing ocean carbon?*” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 16 respondents.

- Phytoplankton/plankton (6)
- Vulnerable marine ecosystems including sponges, corals, reefs (5)
- Seagrasses, macroalgae, salt marsh (3)
- All living organisms, abundance, balance (3)
- Specific fish species (1)
- Large aquatic animals (1)
- Benthos (1)
- Viruses and bacteria (1)
- Humans (1)
- Organic and inorganic carbon (1)

Figure 3.4 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you that removing fish, other animals, plants and algae (like seaweed or plankton) from the ocean removes ocean carbon?” (16 responses).

The emerging or expanding marine activities linked to carbon and climate change most commonly mentioned were offshore renewable energy, deep-sea mining and oil and gas activities (Box 3.6). 41% of respondents answered that they were very concerned about these activities, though responses varied depending on what activities people had in mind (Figure 3.5). For example, one respondent mentioned that their concern related specifically to deep-sea mining. Another respondent emphasised the need for sustainable management for any activity that takes place to minimise negative impacts.

Box 3.6 Themes of the responses to the question: “Are you aware of any new or growing marine activities that are related to carbon and climate change? (Which ones)” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). (17 respondents).

- Offshore marine renewable energy, wind energy (6)
- Deep-sea mining (6)
- Oil and gas exploitation, including deep sea oil and gas exploration (5)
- Carbon capture and storage technologies (2)
- Conservation and restoration (2)
- New aquaculture e.g. farming octopus, algae (2)
- Mesopelagic fisheries (1)
- Carbon credits/offsets (1)
- Dredging (1)
- Marine tourism (1)
- Renewable energy for propulsion (1)

Figure 3.5 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about these activities?” (17 responses).

In terms of what implications ocean carbon and the links with fisheries might have for respondents' work, the most common response related to seeing changes as being part of existing management and fishing practices and efforts to make the fishing industry more sustainable (5 respondents) (Box 3.7). Four respondents were unsure of the implications at this stage, and think that these will not come until there is more evidence and scientific consensus on the impacts of fisheries on ocean carbon. A number of other issues were raised that respondents wanted to address (Box 3.8).

Box 3.7 Themes of the responses to the question: "Based on your responses to the previous questions, will there be implications for you in your work? (e.g. changes to your practices, policies, focal areas, etc.) (Briefly describe)" (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). (15 respondents).

- Implications will be part of continuous/ongoing evolution and efforts of fishing policy, practices and management to become more efficient and sustainable (5)
- Unsure of implications (until there is more evidence) (4)
- The need to assess or know the impacts of climate change on fisheries (2)
- No implications (2)
- Need to increase knowledge, understanding, awareness and dissemination (2)
- Jeopardise the future of traditional fisheries (1)
- Changes will be applied to everyone, not just the high impact fisheries (1)
- Deep-sea mining impacts on fishing (1)

Box 3.8 Are there any other topics related to fishing and ocean carbon, not covered in this survey, that are of interest/concern to you? Briefly describe:

- Food security (2)
- Global warming (2)
- Regarding the impact of fishing and its role in limiting carbon sequestration: Consideration for fishes' physiological processes, such as organic/inorganic carbon fluxes resulting from eating and breathing. And, carbon fluxes and outcomes of large pelagic fish harvests (in thousands of tons) should be compared with the global annual oceanic carbon absorption (around 2.5 billion tons), as the scale of fishing is relatively minor in the context of overall oceanic carbon dynamics and representing only a temporary storage of carbon (1)
- Fishery displacement (1)
- Animal welfare and viewing aquatic animals as being worth more alive rather than being stocks to be exploited (1)
- Ecosystem-based fisheries management
- Climate change
- Scale of impacts compared to other marine activities and land based activities (1)

3.2 High Seas Fisheries – Ocean Carbon Social Ecological System

One of the goals of the workshop was to produce a mental model, together with the stakeholders, of the elements of a high seas fisheries – ocean carbon system and the interactions between those elements. The first step of this was to brainstorm on what elements should be included. This was followed by building the model through discussion of how the elements interact. This type of mental map is a causal model of the system, represented by a network of elements and the relationships between them (Barbrook-Johnson and Penn, 2022). The connections should capture all the complexity in the systems, but notes or annotations can also be used to represent different beliefs. This type of approach is an iterative process, and the map can be built on and further developed over time.

3.2.1 Elements of a High Seas System

In the first step, we identified the elements of the high seas fisheries – ocean carbon system to include in the mental model, and to support an ocean carbon risk assessment. The elements were structured around the categories: sectors, pressures, ecosystem components and ecosystem services or socio-economic factors. Participants of the workshop were asked four questions, in turn:

- What sectors are most relevant in relation to ocean carbon in the high seas?
- What pressures are most relevant in relation to ocean carbon in the high seas?
- What ecosystem elements should be included in the analyses? At what level of detail?
- What ecosystem services and socio-economic factors should be included in the model? i.e. what are the trade-offs you are concerned about?

Participants could suggest their responses through MS Teams polls for each question. The polls appeared as live Word Clouds that participants could view (Figure 3.6). After a first round of answers, prompts (Appendix 7.5) were shown to participants to identify if there were other elements that they would add or remove from these lists. The final list per category can be seen in Table 3.1.

Figure 3.6 Word clouds of elements of the high-seas ocean carbon social-ecological system, as chosen by participants of the workshop. See Table 3.1 for full lists of elements. Elements are categorised under: sectors (or human activities), pressures (mechanisms of change), ecosystem components, and ecosystem services/socio-economic elements.

Table 3.1 Full list of components proposed by participants.

Sector	Mentions
Deep sea mining/mining	9
Fishing (including pelagic and trawling)	9
Shipping and transportation	7
Oil and gas	4
Renewable energy	2
Terrestrial emissions	1
Pressure	Mentions
Removal of biomass/extraction (target and non-target)	6
Sediment disturbance	4
Emissions	3
Climate change	2
Physical loss	2
Acidification	1
Collisions with large mammals and fish	1
Pollution	1
Trophic chain disruption	1
Underwater noise	1
Litter	1
Ecosystem component	Mentions
Phyto- and zooplankton (including viruses, bacteria)	8
Small pelagic fish	3
Fish (e.g. mesopelagics)	3
Invertebrates (e.g. krill)	3
Seasonal variation	2
Trophic interactions	2
Vulnerable marine ecosystems	2
All components contributing to carbon cycle	1
Nutrients	1
Species specific data	1
Spatial distribution	1
Species composition	1
Abundance	1
Pelagic organisms	1
High trophic levels	1
Storms	1
Marine mammals	1
Ecosystem Service/Socio-Economic Factor	Mentions
Food (provision, low carbon, security)	12
Livelihood	3
Carbon sequestration and offset	3
Cultural elements	1
Employment	1
Big Polluters versus Small Fixes	1
Fish welfare	1
Fleet activity (number and size of boats)	1
Technology and innovation	1
Market demand	1
Weather and extreme events	1
Social equity	1

3.2.2 Discussion: Ocean Carbon – Fisheries System Components

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the Marine Institute (MI)/OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Is the aim to find scientific responses or opinions? This will be a mixture of expert and stakeholder knowledge to identify priority areas and knowledge gaps. In terms of modelling, there is a wide range of models in the project for various purposes. For example, the shelf seas ones will include multi-sectoral scenarios. We haven't included offshore renewables in the initial lists for this workshop as we think it's more of a shelf seas issue rather than high seas but if you think we should change that, please let us know.
- How is ocean acidification tackled in this? It affects the way carbon flows and moves in the sea as well, dissolving CaCO₃ etc. The more complex models include temperature metrics, acidification, deoxygenation, etc. These risk assessments generally exclude climate change since it interacts with everything [*i.e. each sector, pressure and ecosystem component*] thus making assessment and interpretation near impossible. Here we are attempting to include it and investigating the best way to do this. We are looking for your input to narrow down the focus on the number of components that we focus on.
- High seas biggest activities are fishing, shipping, mining maybe and cable laying. On the contrary, activity level in the shelf seas is very high and is feeding into the high seas. Agreed, some pressures mentioned are more likely to feed into the high seas rather than actually taking place in the high seas. There are additional activities in high seas such as military activity and research but both have a small footprint in the high seas.
- Bycatch are normally returned to the sea. How does this affect carbon since they aren't removed from the marine system? Carbon may move between species but isn't removed from the sea. Good point. This list is from another project [*as a starting point*], not specifically related to carbon. It may be interesting to look at that aspect, if the body is thrown back, it's a different scale of a carbon impact than the target species that are removed. We may have to consider these two aspects separately.
- Would the body being put back affect the cycling and sinking of the carbon? Yes, potentially. Even when fish are filleted/gutted at sea, that offal is thrown back into the sea and joins the carbon cycle in that way.
- From Researchers: Should we work with groups or individual species? If you choose certain species it will be interesting but from a biodiversity perspective, for carbon I presume you need to look at really big groups, like mesopelagic which is a big group but with lots of uncertainty. It's also theoretical as you don't really have the fishery there. We need to go for big volumes like small pelagic where you're looking at 2-3 million tonnes. Not sure about choosing a particular type of tuna, for example, I would choose the biggest mass and look at that. Also could look at the impacts of bottom fishing on particular corals and the release of carbon from those. Based on the polls pelagic fish should be split into small pelagics and large pelagics. For species elements, we could potentially do parallel assessments; one integrative assessment with large scale components, and a more specific one with particular species, probably of commercial interest to give a more detail-specific case study. Perhaps it would be easier then to link through to specificities to social and economic impact since it can be tied to a particular species and commercial activity.
- Do we need to be more specific? In the assessment of these components, policy is very important, e.g. NGOs may have an interest in limiting fisheries for conservation objectives. All these assessments have to be done in that light, it's a way of massing support of what we want to do,

similar to how fisheries may want to amass support for low carbon fishing methods. In relation to policy, we will be taking it into account through developing scenarios. What are the policy goals and objectives that will dictate the trajectory of where we go? Using policy view can help us develop the scenarios, e.g. how do we maximise the Blue Economy and ensure food for humans? We are interested in trying to capture different policy aspects.

- Is policy, governance and management in relation to deep seas taken into account when weighing up the options (e.g. VMEs)? The assessments are current status assessments usually. If something is banned (e.g. trawling on VMEs), it won't show up in the assessment as it's not current. It may get more complicated in the high seas as something could be banned by some countries and not others. Future scenarios can take into account potential changes in climate, potential closures etc based on policy objectives. It's not clear how we will do this yet, perhaps through ecosystem modelling rather than the risk assessment we are looking at here. There are additional analysis approaches like bow-tie analysis where you look at objectives, state and management/mitigation measures that are in place. We can investigate this further to see if it is a possibility.
- Some fleets have certification and socio-economic standards that are higher than others, which should be taken into account as a socio-economic component of the fishery. Very interesting. Are more sustainable practices carried out by certified fleets leading to lower carbon impacts? This is something we can potentially investigate further.
- How is food security and safety taken into account? Food security is in there, food provisioning as an ecosystem service, and carbon regulation service too. *Added: Food safety is not something we have considered so far; it is currently unclear how it relates to carbon – however suggestions are welcome.*

3.2.3 Conceptual Model of a High Seas Fisheries-Ocean Carbon System

The elements from the first exercise were used as a starting point to build a conceptual model, ensuring the inclusion of the focal elements: ‘fishing’ and ‘ocean carbon’. This was produced live during the workshop via the online MentalModeler software (www.mentalmodeler.org; Gray et al. 2013). Discussion with the participants informed where links should be (i.e. what connections exist). Through this process, the elements in the model evolved, and understanding of the linkages was elucidated. The resulting model is illustrated in Figure 3.7.

The elements included in the final model were:

Sectors	Pressures	Ecosystem Components	Socio-economic elements & Ecosystem Services	Climate
Shipping	Emissions	Plankton	Food provisioning	Temperature
Deep sea mining	Noise	Benthic habitats	Livelihoods	Acidification
Pelagic fishing	Seabed impacts	Fish	Spatial conflict	Ocean Carbon Cycle
Oil and gas	Species extraction (including bycatch)			Global Carbon Cycle

Figure 3.7 Provisional mental model co-produced with stakeholders during the ABNJ workshop, updated with action points, using the software MentalModeler. The elements of the model are represented as boxes and colour indicates the type of element: sectors (orange), pressures (blue), ecosystem components (green), ecosystem services (yellow), socio-economic elements (pink). Grey boxes are elements that can be mechanisms of change but are not necessarily pressures. Links between the nodes are represented by lines. Lines are either positive (elements are positively correlated; blue lines), negative (elements have an inverse relationship; red lines), or unknown (thin black lines). Note: full consistency check of this model is in progress, some amendments may result from this process.

4. Action Items

Action points arising from the meeting

- Summary report to be written and circulated for review and feedback.
- Investigate evidence on the impacts of noise on plankton and assess if this link should be included in the model
- The model (Figure 3.7) will be consistency checked for anomalies and issues, and ground-truthed against available evidence and in consultation with stakeholders in a future session.
- Suggested research questions will be investigated (see emerging themes below) as well as potential other sectors for consideration.
- Additional workshops will be arranged with shelf seas and deep-sea mining stakeholders, and follow-up meetings with this stakeholder group.

5. Conclusions

Active engagement from the invited participants led to a successful outcome for the workshop. Through discussion, survey results and building the conceptual model, some key themes emerged. These can be broken down into high-level themes – overarching themes that are ‘big picture’ and into more specific themes – themes related to more specific activities of fisheries. We have also identified themes related specifically to knowledge and evidence gaps.

High-level themes:

- **Fisheries and Climate Change:** The impacts of climate change on fisheries, how carbon will affect the food web and the implications of these changes for fisheries, and how fisheries can adapt to climate change.
- **Fishing and the Global Carbon Cycle:** How does fishing as an activity compare to other activities at sea (e.g. oil and gas activities), and other activities on land (e.g. farming), particularly in terms of carbon per kg of protein?
- **Fishing and Climate Policy:** Terrestrial and marine policies affect each other and should be considered in tandem to ensure identification of potential trade-offs and socio-economic impacts.
- **Food Security and Fishing Livelihoods:** Management of carbon needs to be balanced with the ecosystem and socio-economic services fish and fisheries and ancillary industries are providing, particularly as future demands for food are expected to increase.

Specific themes:

- **Fishing Practices and the Carbon Cycle:** How do fisheries with more sustainable practices compare to less sustainable fisheries in terms of carbon? How does bycatch, the type of fishing (pelagic versus benthic trawling), and sustainability certification interact with and/or affect the oceanic carbon cycle?
- **Fishing Efficiency:** How do ongoing efforts to improve sustainability and efficiency, e.g. in terms of gear used, distance travelled, fuel use etc., contribute to reducing carbon impacts?

Key knowledge and evidence gaps:

- Participants perceive a **lack of evidence** on the links between fishing and the ocean carbon cycle in general
- A key knowledge gap is on the **biological carbon pump** and interactions with fisheries

The above points and themes will guide the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU. They will help form the basis of scenarios to test using a range of modelling approaches, including Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN), and help inform the basis of an ecological risk assessment centred around carbon.

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7. Appendices

7.1 Agenda

Time (GMT)	Program
13.00 – 13.30	Introduction to workshop, housekeeping, and OceanICU project
13.30 – 14.30	Presentation and open discussion on high seas fisheries and carbon
14.30-14.40	Results from the pre-workshop survey
14.40 - 15.10	Exercise: elements of an ocean carbon-high seas fisheries system
15.10 – 15.30	Break
15.30 – 16.40	Exercise: co-producing a model of an ocean carbon-high seas fisheries system
16.40 – 17.00	Wrap up and final words

7.2 Acronyms

- (e)NGO: (environmental) non-governmental organisation
- BCP: Biological Carbon Pump
- CDR: Carbon Dioxide Removal
- CO₂: Carbon dioxide
- COV-IEO, CSIC: Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo, Instituto Español de Oceanografía - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
- DGMARE: Directorate-General Mare, EU Commission for maritime affairs and fisheries
- DST: Decision Support Tool
- EBFM: Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management
- EBM: Ecosystem-Based Management
- ES: Ecosystem Services
- EU: European Union
- FPO: Fish Producers Organisation
- HVO: Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
- ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
- IEO-CSIC: Instituto Español de Oceanografía - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spanish National Research Council)
- IFPO: Irish Fish Producers Organisation
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- IPMA: Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere)
- ISE FPO: Irish South and East Fish Producers Organisation
- MSC: Marine Stewardship Council
- NAFO: Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organisation
- NEAFC: North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission
- NET: Negative Emissions Technologies
- NWWAC: North Western Waters Advisory Council
- OceanICU: Integrated Carbon Understanding – the project behind this workshop: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>
- RMFO: Regional Fisheries Management Organisation
- SST: Sea Surface Temperature
- UAPF: Union des Armateurs à la Pêche de France
- VME: Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems

7.3 List of Organisations Represented by Workshop Attendees

	Affiliation
1	North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC)
2	IPMA-Portuguese Institute of Ocean and Atmosphere; NAFO-Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization
3	Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA)
4	Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA)
5	Rederscentrale
6	North Western Waters Advisory Council
7	Aquatic Life Institute
8	Irish South and East Fish Producers Organisation
9	Pelagic Freezer Trawler Association
10	Cornelis Vrolijk
11	Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). European Commission
12	Europêche
13	IEO-CSIC
14	Heriot-Watt University (and Marine Stewardship Council)
15	Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NAFO)
16	Fisheries and Oceans Canada
17	Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO-CSIC)
18	UAPF

7.4 Resource List

- Article on the negligible impact of Kiribati's MPA: <https://www.spc.int/updates/news/media-release/2023/01/are-marine-protected-areas-effective-for-tuna-conservation>
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- EBFA's page on science, including references to carbon: <https://bottomfishingalliance.eu/latest-scientific-news/>
- Ecobusiness: Seabed mining could sink the fishing industry: <https://www.eco-business.com/opinion/seabed-mining-could-sink-the-fishing-industry/#:~:text=Increased%20sediment%20concentrations%20in%20the,diluted%20by%20the%20sediment%20particles>
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- Stakeholder Mailing List Sign Up for OceanICU <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUjoin>
- The EU Parliament's motion for a resolution on Norway's recent decision to advance seabed mining in the Arctic: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/B-9-2024-0095_EN.html
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7.5 Socio-ecological system Components

Sectors

Agriculture
Fishing
Land-based Industry
Military
Nuclear
Research
Shipping
Telecommunications
Tourism/Recreation
Waste Water
Mining
Oil & Gas
Ocean NETS/CDR
Aquaculture
Dredging

Pressures

Abrasion
Bycatch
Contaminating Compounds
Electromagnetic Fields
Incidental Loss
Invasive Species
Litter
Noise
Non-living Resources
Organic Matter
Radionuclides
Sealing
Siltation/Smothering
Species Extraction
Thermal changes
GHG emissions (to air)
pH changes
Salinity changes
Death/injury by collision
Precipitations change

Ecosystem Components

Cephalopods
Demersal Elasmobranchs
Demersal Fish
Pelagic Elasmobranchs
Pelagic Fish
Deep Sea Elasmobranchs
Deep Sea Fish
Reptiles
Seabirds
Marine Mammals
Epipelagic
Mesopelagic
Slope Rock & Reef
Slope Sediment
Deep Sea Rock & Reef
Deep Sea Sediment

Ecosystem Services

Seafood - wild
Seafood - Aquaculture
Raw materials (Biotic/Abiotic)
Genetic Materials
Nursery populations and habitats
Refuge habitats
Global climate regulation
Feeding grounds
Chemical composition of oceans and atmosphere
Cultural services

Socio-Economic Factors

Wages
Fish prices
Fuel prices
Gentrification
Fleet diversification
Safety at Sea
Equity
Quota
Management
Governance
Enforcement
Fishing Behaviour
Community Impacts
Processing/Processors